

INTERPRETATION OF WORD FORMATION IN UZBEK

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Annotation: the interpretation of word formation in Uzbek in the article was discussed.

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Within the system of word formation, the base of word formation, the meaning of word formation, word means of formation, method of formation of words, type of formation of words, pattern of formation of words concepts embodied. All these are necessary for the language and important. In particular, the importance of the concept called the base of word formation is important and fundamental. "This concept is like a word-making tool, a word-making template consists of the relationship of internal parts. A separate base of word formation its importance is that it serves as the basis of motivation in the creation of a new word will pass. Language as the basis of motivation in the process of word formation in addition to the own stratum units of the lexicon, as well as the assimilated stratum units role and importance is great"

The creation of a new word by adding words, one the formation of a word in a second group from a word in a group is the language of word formation determines that it is a unique separate system in its construction.

In Uzbek linguistics, it is a word in the literature mentioned above the following methods are shown:

- 1) affixation method;
- 2) phonetic method;

- 3) semantic method;
- 4) composition method;
- 5) abbreviation method.

1. Affixation method. The modern Uzbek language has a wide range of word formations the most productive, leading type used is the affixation method. Join the base and that's it word formation related to the meaning of the base, but with a new lexical meaning The affix that takes part in making is called a word-forming affix (supplement). New Affixation, which is the leading means of forming words with lexical meaning, is Uzbek in the language, it has the character of suffixation, that is, formative suffixes are formative is added to the end of the base. For example, terim-chi, apple-zor, linguist-scientist, aq-la, ish-la, such as knowledgeable, disciplined. Partially from other languages (mainly Tajik) in word formation prefixes are also used. For example, ba-power, bar-time, priceless, out of place, like, unfaithful, rich. Such construction is mainly quality found in the series.

Word-forming affixes are often from one word group to another word group forms a new lexical unit. For example, summer, winter - noun, summer, winter - adjective; work, saw - horse; work, saw - verb; white, good quality, whiten, improve - verb; broom, orfe'l, broom-gi, or-ak-ot kabi.

Sometimes a word-forming affix is a word-formation that is unique to a group possible This is more characteristic of the horse family. For example, work-work-work, iron-work-work, cart-cart-kash (-word); sand-sand-lok, stone-stone-lok, apricot-apricot-zor, til-til -such as scholar, literature-literature-scholar, Uzbek-Uzbek-Istan.

The system of forming words in a language is linguistic, which is opposed to the language itself does not rely only on units. A foreign language that is assimilated into a language in the process of word formation the role of lexical elements is not insignificant. Uzbek language is a vivid example of this it can be seen through concrete actions in the process of making it.

The lexicon of the Uzbek language contains a large number of words borrowed from other languages organizes. Among them, there are special vocabulary units specific to Arabic and Persian-Tajik languages is important. They are considered as an external source of enrichment of the Uzbek language.

The source of internal enrichment is the creation of words with the help of additions, the addition of words the emergence of a new word, its development according to its meaning and pronunciation as a result of which a new word appears. Arabic, Persian-Tajik in the lexicon of the Uzbek language in the internal enrichment of the Uzbek language words participate in all these processes. Arabic and Persian-Tajik dictionary appropriations are especially active in the process of forming affixal words. Uzbek to them a lot of lexical units were formed from the addition of affixes.

Addition of single -dosh or -chi affixes to Arabic lexical acquisitions thanks to a confidant, classmate, schoolmate, colleague, advisor, compatriot, interlocutor, sex; there are many founders, communicators, ghazal singers, bayaz singers, etc new words are formed.

Word-forming affixes are productive or less productive depending on their use in speech and is divided into useless affixes.

An affix is a powerful builder, serving to form many new words is called For example, what about work, what about service, what about hunting, what about ma, show, peace, goodness, size, laugh, push, sweep, winter, work, saw, white, good-la, like combing-la.

An affix that is less involved in word formation is called a less productive affix. For example: scythe, taro-q, head-white, labor-kash, cart-kash, swim-gich, qir-gich, like gathering, competition. An affix that does not now form a new unit is called a sterile formant. Unproductive affixes are usually found in only a few words. For example: bag-agon, chop-agaon, sez-gir, cut-kir, work-chan, yuat-chan, san-a, cut-kin.

Regardless of which language is in the acquisition base, the resulting new lexical units are considered a special asset of the Uzbek language. E. Begmatov the Uzbek language has its own internal lexical resource, the Uzbek language itself the words created over the centuries are called Uzbek words. Such the creator and owner of words is the Uzbek people and the Uzbek language. Because Uzbek words The Uzbek-speaking ethnos creates on the basis of the capabilities of its language is a linguistic creator, "that is, Uzbek words are the own word of the Uzbek language, its own is a product".

The birth of affixes also occurs: some words are affixes even though it has fulfilled its function and started approaching the following morpheme, still will not become an affix. These are considered affixoids.

2. Phonetic method. Making a word by this method involves 2 events: 1) the word creating a new word by making a phonetic change (sound change) in its structure. For example, chalk-grey, mountain-stone, eye-see, stone-tooth (based on the sign of hardness);

"In language, in general, with the emergence of a new meaning, a new word, not yet in the dictionary or as a variant of "unable to become independent" It is important that the walking element enters the language vocabulary system as a separate word:

3. The analysis of words such as spread, write, yon, yang, fuel, fuel shows that (there are many such words), to many words in the historical development of the Uzbek language moving gradually from phonetic differentiation to semantic differentiation incident happened.

4. Composition method. There is more than one way to make words by composition combining the constituent base in terms of meaning and content, a new lexical unit is a compound is word formation. The difference between a compound word and a simple word is that in a simple word there is one independent meaningful part.

5. A compound word has more than one. Word This type of construction is one of the most active methods in the Uzbek language. For example, gulbeor, like a peanut, a triangle. A compound word has one whole lexical meaning - one complex concept and integral formation - the integrity of the grammatical concept, phonetic characterized by integrity. So it is one word. Parts of a compound word there is no grammatical connection between them. But there is a semantic connection.

In general, there are opinions about the formation of words variety can be encountered.

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